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Influence of Stress Among Nigerian Workers: The Therapeutic Management Strategies for Effective Living in the Society

¹Otakpo Chile, Ph.D; ²Okogbule, Felix Sunday, (Ph.D) & ³Jaja, Louis Emmanuel, Ph.D

¹Department of Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counselling
Faculty of Education

Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria
angelchile300@ust.edu.ng/07067884802

²Department of Educational Foundations
Faculty of Education

Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria
felixokogbule@ust.edu.ng/08037026624

³Faculty of Education

Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria
kingdsdody80@yahoo.com/08180844130

ABSTRACT

The paper captured the disaster that Nigerian worker faced during their working years or days. The study also revealed that Nigerian workers are passing through hell and if not properly checked, it would take their lives. The paper also discussed the definition of stress, such as the means that triggers one's health or body. The paper discussed the developmental stages of stress and the sources of stress, such as poor remuneration, late payment of salaries, poor interpersonal relationship. Lack of promotion and delayed in retirement benefits etc. The paper also discussed the consequences of stress such as health challenges, disease in opportunities and interpersonal relationship. The study also discussed the tools for effective living, such as exercise, happiness and relaxation finally, the paper discussed the management stress such as happiness, daily exercise and frequent needed check-up.

Keywords: Influence, Stress, Nigerian Workers, Therapeutic management strategy.

INTRODUCTION

Everyday stress among Nigeria workers is on the increase. This could be as a result of workers expectations not being met, poor work environment, and their inability to meet up with their physiological needs. A worker, no matter where he is working, is expected to satisfy his basic needs such as, shelter, clothing, housing, transportation, feeding, sex, medical care etc.

Obarango (2020) opined that, however, and unfortunately, most Nigeria workers are increasingly finding it difficult to fulfill these basic needs. This situation makes the majority of the workers to experience high level of stress as some of them resort to other jobs or business in order to make ends meet.

Odumangu (2024) opined that financial stress which is a major source of workers stress could easily trigger health challenges. Stress, which can be explained as the body mechanism operating at a disequilibrium level arises when there is a pressure above an individual's level of normal functioning that makes him take extra steps in order to cope with the situation and can be dangerous. Overdose stress in a worker can make him to be in a reflective and open to health challenges, thereby making life to be meaningless.

Akanda, (2024) listed the following as sources of stress. The stress among Nigerian workers are as follows: Poor remuneration, i.e., then salaries are insufficient to enable them satisfy their basic needs.

- Late payment of salaries
- Poor physical facilities at work places as work often their offices are poorly furnished and ill equipped.
- Poor interpersonal relationship
- Lack of promotion
- Poor opportunities to advance in their careers
- Work overload
- Role conflict
- Retirement benefits etc.

Ola, (2015) opined that these stressors propel stress among Nigerians workers. These prove that when Nigerians workers are poorly paid, it could make the worker face some challenges such as not being able to cope or take care of himself or herself, Nigerian workers cannot leave in a decent house because of lack of money. This imbalance situation has put pressure and thinking among Nigerian workers. Most Nigerian workers cannot pay their children school fee and feed well. This condition had triggered a barrel of pressure among Nigerian workers and place them as suffer men and woman.

Chile, (2015) stated that overdose stress can kill, subject people into thinking and trigger chronic stress or hypertension. Thinking could lead to high blood pressure (Bp), which is one of the most killer disease we have today in the society. This high blood pressure can trigger stroke among Nigerians workers if not properly checked.

Stress is not always harmful and every workers need a level of stress to perform well. When stress is the high frequency, it activates a level of energy that helps the worker to succeed. Apparently, when stress is above the optimized level, it becomes dangerous and can motivate some ill – consequences that can make the individual or worker ineffective. Therefore, every worker should strive to maintain a balance as regards stress for good living.

Manda, (2016) stress that what constitutes stress to a worker may not constitute to others.

What is Stress?

Stress can be defined as the inability of the body to absorb normally as regards to function at an accepted level. It is also a state which comprises heavy load to man's functionality.

What is a worker?

A worker is anybody who is doing a job for which he earns an income. A worker is also a person that earns a token at the end of the month.

THE PREVENTIVE MEASURE:

Sandra, (2019) state the following as the preventive measure, applied to manage stress.

Therapy

Therapy is a strict measure or strategy taken by Nigerian worker whose stress has ravaged to curb it.

Work overload

This is a situation where a Nigerian worker observed to avoid stress. It is a condition where a worker do a little work as a panacea to avert stress

Thinking less

This is another measure which a Nigerian worker applied to avert stress.

Developmental Stages of Stress

Alex (2018) opined that this idea states that life is made up of developmental stages and that each stage is characterized by certain tasks which the individual to meet up certain task or expectation can as well lead to stress. This inability could trigger health challenges.

The ability of an individual to win a task of a particular stage will engender good life.

Sources of Stress

Poor remuneration: The workers salary is not able to take care of his needs. The situation is becoming bad or unbecoming as a result of increase of things in Nigeria.

Late payment of salaries: Late payment of salaries has caused difficulty for the worker to meet up with their immediate needs. Delay of payment can trigger financial stress and health challenges.

Urgent need to meet up deadline: This comes when a worker is expected to meet up task and could not.

Absenteeism: The worker is constantly absent in his workplace.

Consequences of stress on workers

Sango (2020), list the following consequences:

Psychological effects: These may include depression withdrawal, anxiety, aggression, frustration, apathy, emotional instability and loss of self – esteem.

Poor interpersonal relationships: A worker experiencing a high level of stress may be maladaptive in relating with his fellow workers or his supervisor or even family members.

Health challenges: Some ailments like ulcer, high blood pressure, headache, fever, stroke, sexual dysfunction, fatigue, low body immunity, heart attack, loss of appetite, cancer, flu and insomnia are experiences.

Decrease in Job performance: The worker performs below optimum level, He may not be able to achieve set target.

Exhaustion: The worker is easily tired and worn-out.

Loss of Concentration: The worker is not focused. His attention is diffused and not what he is doing.

Poor eating pattern: This involves loss of appetite. The workers eating pattern suddenly beings too depreciate.

Death: The extreme form of unchecked acute stress is death. Most often stress might manifest in form of high blood pressure, which if not checked might develop to stroke and subsequently death.

Absenteeism: Stress can cause workers to be consistently absent in their work places as a result of health challenges or apathy. This altitude if not checked on time could result in low productivity.

NDA, (2025) mentioned the stress management strategies: They are as follows:

Exercise: Exercise activate and help the body healthy. Regular exercises help the body to be functional in order to fight certain diseases. It also helps the body to maintain an optimum level of immunity necessary to word off chronic stress. A relatively moderate level of physical activity rather heavy exercises is enough to make a worker healthy. At least 30 minutes moderate physical activity is suggested to effective living. Fast walk, jogging, swimming, cycling, dancing, using mention but a few, are enough physical activities that can help to prevent high level stress.

Happiness: This is a management strategy that is very effective in minimizing extreme stress. As a worker, always strive to be happy. Try as much as possible to laugh whenever it is possible. Happiness creates internal joy that helps to destroy chronic stress. Let the moment of happiness outweigh the moment of sadness everyday in your life.

Relaxation: As a worker, always find time to relax after the days hard labour. Relaxation helps to calm tensed muscles provoked by overdose stress. Everyday work without relaxation can easily provoke chronic stress, make the body to breakdown and can cause sudden collapse and death. Relaxation helps to restore the body's homeostasis. Workers are advised to take at least 20 minutes nap in their offices everyday especially when they have deadlines to meet.

Ukanna (2011) listed the effective living strategy they are as follows:

- Always participate in religious activities. Be a good Christian or Muslim or traditionalist.

- Try as much as possible to maintain cordial relationships with those around you (Co – Workers, family members, friends and church members)
- Try to be humorous, laugh as much as you can every day. Humor is a good antidote to chronic stress and negative life events.
- Avoid unnecessary jealousy. Appreciate the good in other people.
- Think positively: Positive thinking rekindles happiness which destroys overdose stress and help in effective living
- Always strive to help the less privileged. Be contented with what you have.
- Avoid self – medication. Visit medical personal when sick
- Share your problems with trusted friends and others.
- Always maintain cordial relationship with others.
- Go on vacation: As a worker, go on vacation once a year. Going on vacation help the worker to change environment and to rest for a period of time that will enable him to reinvigorate.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Government should understand that workers needs all necessary amenities or equipment to live and live well.
- Government should take proper care of Nigerian workers and provide enabling environment for them.
- Government should ensure workers plight are in order.
- Government should make sure workers experience stress free.
- Government should be proactive in delivery of the mandate given to them by the masses.
- Workers should obey the necessary rules and regulations that will enhance their health conditions and make them live well.
- Workers should adhere strictly to the spelt – out conditions that will set them free from stress.
- Workers should try to avoid stress all the time

CONCLUSION

The paper has discussed the meaning of stress properly and list out various definitions. The paper also discussed the sources, symptoms, brief, theories, effects of stress and others. The paper advised the women to keep to the rules and regulations governing human conduct in order to be free from stress.

REFERENCES

- Akanda, D. (2024). The ego and id. Uyo: Langa Press.
- Alex, U. (2018) Environmental influence on mental health, and health harzards of the human environment Casablanca: Aelo printing press.
- Nda, D (2025). Every day stress and its management. Port Harcourt: Paragraphics.
- Obarango, I. (2020). Stress management. Owerri: Saki, book Ltd.
- Ochumagu, S. (2024). Essentials of psychology: Exploration and Application. New York; Kanela Publishing Co.
- Ola, S. (2015). Psychological Stress. In AcDry –Hill International Encyclopedia of Science and technology. New York: ACDry – Hill.
- Sandra, D. (2019). Role conflict and ambiguity as critical variable in a model organizational behaviour.
- Sango, U. (2020). The psychological Alamanc. Australia: Brooks – cole publishing Co.
- Ukanna, S. (2021). The stress of life. New York: Mcgrand – Hill.